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The Central Italy's 1997-2009-2016 Seismic Sequences: a comparison of surface deformation from a review of DInSAR results.

Carlo Alberto Brunori
INGV- Perugia, Italy
carloalberto.brunori@ingv.it

Massimiliano R.Barchi, Massimiliano Porreca,
Laura Melelli
Dip.di Fisica e Geologia Università di Perugia
{massimiliano.barchi, massimiliano.porreca,
laura.melelli}@unipg.it

Vincenzo De Novellis, Diego Reale, Eugenio Sansosti
Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of Environment (IREA)
National Research Council (CNR) Napoli, Italy
{denovellis.v, reale.d, sansosti.e@irea.cnr.it}

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Abstract — Between 1997 and 2017, the Central Apennines experienced three seismic sequences—Colfiorito-Gualdo Tadino (1997-1998), L'Aquila (2009), and Amatrice-Visso-Norcia (2016-2017)—which share similar characteristics in terms of fault kinematics and crustal structure. These sequences, driven by extensional tectonics, can be viewed as resulting from the longitudinal propagation of a complex NNW-SSE trending normal fault setting along a distance of about 130 km. These seismic sequences can be interpreted as manifestations of the same geodynamic process, occurring within a relatively short spatial and temporal range in comparable tectonic and geological settings. This repetition creates a natural laboratory where, using similar observation techniques, the impact of these events on the Earth's surface can be quantitatively assessed and analysed. In this study, we review the surface deformation induced by four mainshocks of these sequences using InSAR data from SAR missions ERS (1992-2000), Envisat (2003-2011), and Sentinel-1 (2014-present), with the aim of proposing a direct comparison of the size, shape, and spatial distribution of ground displacement across different events. The results highlight both commonalities and differences of ground deformation patterns across the different analysed events. This methodological approach, after the experiences acquired in more than 30 years of InSAR-derived observations, offers a deeper understanding of the potential and limitations of InSAR for monitoring earthquake-induced surface deformation. By considering four different earthquakes, occurred in the same geological context, we will compare and discuss the relationships between the observed surface deformation and the magnitude and fault mechanism at depth of the causative events.

I. INTRODUCTION

Italy is among the most tectonically active regions, as evidenced by historical and recent earthquakes [1]. The tectonic activity is marked by compressional mechanisms along the Alpine and Apennine fronts and extensional mechanisms along the Apennine belt, which extend northeast-southwest to Calabria, where the orientation shifts to northwest-southeast, reflecting the curvature of the Calabrian arc. The Apennines are characterized predominantly by extensional seismicity along the ridge at depths of 10–15 km. Advances in data acquisition, including Differential Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (DInSAR) and seismology, allow detailed analysis of seismic sequences and faulting processes. Since 1997, three major seismic sequences, nucleated within same tectonic settings (i.e., extensional environments) along the Central and Northern Apennines chain, causing several casualties and large damage: the 1) 1997 1 Colfiorito, 2) the 2009 L'Aquila, and the most recent 3) 2016-2017 Central Italy seismic sequences [2- 6, Fig. 1, Table 1]. The aim of this study is to carry out a consistent comparison across the three sequences by means the analysis of DInSAR products, thus better identifying common patterns in the deformation fields. By comparing the spatial and geometric relationships of the deformed masses with the corresponding fault sources, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanical processes governing these seismic events and their spatial impact on the landforms of this region.

Figure 1. The 1997-2017 seismic sequences in the Central Apennines

I. MATERIAL AND METHODS

An interferogram is generated by processing a pair of SAR images captured over the same area at different times. This process, known DInSAR, involves comparing the phase difference between the two images to detect subtle changes in the Earth's surface. The resulting interferogram displays deformation patterns as a series of concentric colored fringes, each representing a displacement of approximately half the radar wavelength (e.g., ~ 2.8 cm) for C-band sensors available and exploited for the purposes of this work.

Deformation fringes in an interferogram represent phase differences between two SAR images acquired at different times over the same area. Each fringe (or cycle of color) corresponds to a specific displacement of the ground along the satellite's Line of Sight (LOS), typically equal to half the radar wavelength. The fringes provide a visual representation of ground deformation patterns, allowing scientists to quantify surface movements with high precision. The concentric pattern of a series of fringes indicates a localized deformation source, often associated with phenomena such as in our case earthquakes, but also for volcanic inflation/deflation, or subsidence. The direction of motion can be inferred from the shape and distribution of the fringes. The phase shift measured in an interferogram is a cyclic signal, meaning that the radar measures phase differences within a range of 0 to 2π .

Once the phase shift exceeds 2π , it "resets" creating a cyclic pattern known as phase wrapping. The interferogram represented using fringes is called "wrapped". To measure the total ground displacement, the phase must be "unwrapped" by adding successive 2π cycles to account for the cumulative displacement. This process is critical for distinguishing between large and small displacements and for deriving continuous deformation maps.

In summary, deformation fringes provide valuable insight into ground displacement patterns, and the cyclic delay of the SAR signal allows precise measurements of these displacements. However, interpreting these fringes requires careful phase unwrapping to account for the periodic nature of the radar signal and to convert the cyclic phase values into real-world displacement measurements.

TABLE I. THE 4 MAIN SHOCKS PARAMETERS FOR THE CENTRAL ITALY 1997-2016 SEISMIC SEQUENCES

#	Locality	date	Mw	depth
1	COLFIORITO	SEPT. 27, 1997	6.0	7.5
2	L'AQUILA	APR., 09, 2009	6.3	8
3	AMATRICE	AUG., 24, 2016	6.1	8
3	NORCIA	OCT., 30, 2016	6.5	7

On 26 September 1997, a Mw 6.0 earthquake struck the Central Apennines region of Central Italy (Fig. 1) [7, 8] near the Colfiorito village; the mainshock occurred at a depth of 7.5 km, along the approximately 12-km-long Mt. Pennino-Mt. Prefoglio normal fault, which is part of the Apenninic extensional system [9]. This event was followed by 5,410 aftershocks with $M_w \geq 1.6$, including two notable events on 6 October and 14 October, with magnitudes Mw 5.4 and Mw 5.6, respectively. Additionally, six months later, on 3 April 1998, another earthquake with a magnitude of Mw 5.1 was recorded. The ground displacements caused by the Colfiorito earthquake were investigated through Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar measurements (DInSAR) acquired via ERS satellites. A selection of such interferogram is shown in Figure 2a and 2b for ascending and descending orbit, respectively; the corresponding displacement maps (Fig. 2 i, j) reveal a maximum displacement along the radar line of sight (LOS) of approximately 25 cm. The largest subsidence was observed on the hanging wall block, consistent with a normal faulting mechanism. On 6 April 2009, a Mw 6.3 earthquake took place at a depth of 8 km, along the approximately 15-18 km-long Paganica normal fault [10,11]; it was followed by 19,939 aftershocks with $M_w \geq 0.1$, the strongest of which was a Mw 5.4 earthquake on 7 April (Fig. 1). Ground displacements associated with the L'Aquila earthquake were analysed using DInSAR measurements from ENVISAT satellites, derived from both ascending and descending orbits (Fig. 2c, d, k, l). Figures 2k, l display displacement maps from ascending and

descending orbits, based on acquisitions from 11 March to 15 April 2009 and 1 February to 12 April 2009, respectively. As highlighted by [5], the deformation patterns retrieved reveal an asymmetric distribution of LOS displacement. In the northwestern region, LOS subsidence values of 17-18 cm and 23-24 cm were observed for the ascending and descending orbits, respectively. Conversely, the northeastern region exhibited a maximum LOS uplift of 4-5 cm, visible only in the descending map. The vertical deformation map highlights a maximum subsidence of 25 cm on the hanging wall block, consistent with the normal faulting mechanism [5].

Figure 2. Interferograms for data acquired in both ascending and descending (ASC and DESC) orbits of the four mainshocks: “wrapped” deformation maps ERS (a-b); Envisat (c-d); Sentinel 1(e-h); the i-p images are the above deformation maps “unwrapped” with the displacements expressed in cm.

Finally, the 2016-2017 Central Italy seismic sequence began with the Mw 6.0 Amatrice earthquake on 24 August 2016, which activated the northernmost segment of the SW-dipping Mt. Gorzano extensional fault and the southernmost section of the SW-dipping Mt. Vettore Fault System. Subsequently, on 26 October, two earthquakes with magnitudes Mw 5.4 and Mw 5.9 occurred near Visso, affecting the northern portion of the Mt. Vettore Fault System. The sequence culminated on 30 October with the Mw 6.5 Norcia earthquake, the largest event of the series, located at a depth of approximately 7 km along the Mt. Vettore

Fault System. Additionally, in the January 2017 four significant events (Mw 5.1, 5.5, 5.4, and 5.0) were recorded in the Campotosto area south of Amatrice, originating from the deeper portions of the northwestern segment of the Campotosto fault at depths between 9–11 km [12]. This entire sequence occurred within a seismic gap situated between the 1997 Colfiorito and 2009 L’Aquila earthquakes (Fig. 1) and more than 100,000 events (Mw \geq 0.1) were recorded by the INGV seismometric network. All major earthquakes were characterized by normal faulting mechanisms, consistent with the NE–SW extension direction that defines this sector of the Central Apennines. Ground displacements associated with the mainshocks were analysed using Sentinel-1 data from both ascending and descending orbits. Interferometric pairs with minimal phase artifacts (e.g., atmospheric delays and decorrelation noise) were selected to ensure spatial coverage and coherence (Fig. 2 e, f, m, n). Fig. 2m, n shows the displacement maps derived from the acquisitions of 21-27 August 2016 and 15-27 August 2016 respectively showing an ellipsoidal deformation pattern, characterized by two lobes elongated in the NNW-SSE direction. The Line of Sight (LOS) deformation map showed a maximum subsidence of 20 cm on the hanging wall block, consistent with a normal faulting mechanism.

The ground displacements caused by the Mw 6.5 Norcia earthquake (30 October 2016) were similarly analysed using Sentinel-1 DInSAR measurements from ascending and descending orbits (Fig. 2g, h, o, p). The displacement analysis revealed two NNW–SSE striking lobes, and deformation maps were combined to determine vertical and east-west displacement components (Fig. 2o, p) [4]. The LOS deformation map highlights a maximum subsidence of 70 cm on the hanging wall block and a maximum uplift of 10 cm on the adjacent footwall block. These represent the largest ground displacements ever recorded in Italy using the DInSAR technique, caused by an earthquake.

II. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, both “wrapped” and “unwrapped” interferograms capturing the deformations associated with the main events of the 1997, 2009, and 2016 seismic sequences in the Apennines are shown and compared to allow both qualitative and quantitative analysis (Fig. 2). Preliminary observation highlights differences in the quality of the interferometric fringes (Fig. 2a-h) and the derived displacement fields (Fig. 2i-p). As expected, the quality of the results improves continuously through time: for the 1997 Colfiorito earthquake, the ERS acquisition pairs from both ascending and descending orbits (Fig. 2a-b) show discontinuous measurements, with grainy and poorly defined images, particularly for the ascending pair (Fig. 2i-j). In contrast, better results were obtained with ENVISAT acquisitions (Fig. 2c-

d) for the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake, and even more detailed results were achieved using Sentinel-1 data (Fig. 2e-h) for the 2016 Amatrice and Norcia earthquakes. Sentinel-1 acquisitions offer higher detail in the distribution and continuity of the interferometric fringes and the derived displacement maps (Fig. 2 k-l), offering a clearer identification of the affected areas and rate of ground subsidence or uplift.

This study provides a comprehensive comparison of the ground deformation patterns associated with three major seismic sequences in Central Italy, spanning 1997 to 2016. Using DInSAR techniques, significant insights were gained into the variability and consistency of deformation fields caused by extensional faulting mechanisms in the Apennine region.

The results underline the progression in satellite technology and its impact on the quality of interferometric measurements. While ERS data allowed a first assessment of the 1997 Colfiorito sequence, ENVISAT and Sentinel-1 data offered increasingly detailed and reliable results for the 2009 L'Aquila and 2016 Amatrice-Visso-Norcia events, respectively. This progression highlights the role of technological advancements in refining our understanding of seismic phenomena.

The analysis of displacement fields revealed not only shared characteristics but also significant differences in deformation geometry, spatial distribution, and magnitudes across the sequences. These variations are closely linked to the faulting mechanisms and regional geological context, underscoring the importance of site-specific studies for seismic risk assessment.

Moreover, analysing the differences in the topographic response to similar seismic events (in terms of depth, magnitude and geological context) opens the way to observing other variables in ground deformation, as the role of topographic parameters as the relief energy or the spatial relationship between the fault lines as a key factor in the topographic surface model.

Future work will aim to integrate these observations with source modelling to establish a more detailed relationship between fault dynamics and surface deformation. By coupling advanced geodetic techniques with geological and seismological data, we can further improve our predictive capabilities and support efforts in seismic hazard mitigation.

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